

MUSIC AS AN EFFECTIVE MEANS OF AESTHETIC EDUCATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Annotation: Organized educational activities for musical and aesthetic education begin already at a younger preschool age. In kindergarten, with the help of a music director and educators, children are introduced to singing, acquire the skills of listening to music, develop rhythmic movements, and play children's musical instruments. The combination of mental and physical development, morality and aesthetic attitude to life and art are the necessary conditions for the formation of a holistic personality. The achievement of this goal is largely facilitated by the correct organization of the aesthetic education of preschoolers.

Keywords: musical education, method, aesthetic education, musical image, creative imagination, aesthetic perception

INTRODUCTION. The aesthetic education of preschool children is aimed at developing the ability to perceive, feel and understand the beautiful, notice good and bad, act creatively independently, thereby becoming involved in various types of artistic activity. One of the effective means of aesthetic education is music. In order for music to fulfill this important function, it is necessary to develop general musicality in preschool children.

Firstly, musicality is the ability of a child to feel the character, mood of a piece of music, to empathize with what he heard, to show an emotional attitude, to understand the musical image. Music excites the little listener, evokes responses, introduces life phenomena, gives rise to associations.

Secondly, musicality is the child's ability to listen, compare, evaluate the most vivid and understandable musical phenomena. This requires the preschooler to have an elementary musical and auditory culture, arbitrary auditory attention directed to certain means of expression.

Thirdly, musicality is a manifestation of a child's creative attitude to music. Listening to music, the child in his own way represents an artistic image, conveying it in singing, playing, dancing.

With the development of general musicality in preschool children, an emotional attitude to music appears, hearing improves, and creative imagination is born. The experiences of children acquire a peculiar aesthetic coloring.

V.A. Sukhomlinsky wrote: "The emotionality of nature, characteristic of a morally and aesthetically educated person, is expressed in the fact that the heart becomes receptive to a kind word, teaching, advice, parting words. If you want the word to teach you how to live, so that your pets strive for goodness, educate the subtlety, emotional sensitivity of a young heart. Among the numerous means of influencing the young heart, music occupies an important place.

In the methodology of musical education of children, along with general pedagogical methods, methods are used that are determined by the aesthetic essence and intonational nature of musical art.

N. A. Vetlugina, based on the tasks and essence of musical and aesthetic education, developed four pedagogical methods:

- a method of encouraging empathy and emotional responsiveness to the beautiful in the world around, aimed at enriching the emotional and sensory experience of the child;
- method of persuasion in the process of formation of aesthetic perception;
- method of exercise in practical actions;
- method of search situations that encourage creative and practical act

Methods of musical education are defined as the actions of a teacher aimed at the general musical and aesthetic development of preschool children. The methods are based on the active interaction between an adult and a child and are aimed at educating children in an aesthetic attitude to music, emotional response, musical sensitivity, evaluative attitude, and expressive performance. The use of methods depends on specific educational and educational tasks, on the nature of various types of musical activity, the situation, the source of information, etc.

The expressive performance of music is a necessary condition for conveying to the listener the features of a musical work. The performance of music should be bright enough, temperamental and expressive. Only then it is possible to evoke an emotional response in children, aesthetic experiences, and thereby achieve the desired pedagogical effect.

The aesthetic experiences of a person constitute the unity of the emotional and conscious, therefore, it is necessary to convince not only by the direct influence of music, but also by organizing the focused attention of children, explaining the theme, content, and expressive musical means.

Music is, to some extent, the language of feelings. Music excites, creates a certain mood and thus evokes reciprocal thoughts, makes the child think. It is necessary to clarify, in a word, to strengthen the experiences of preschoolers.

The teacher should verbally evoke a certain commonality of thoughts, experiences and direct the attention of children to the features of the means of musical expression of a particular work. It is also necessary to encourage the correct children's reactions to music.

The method of persuasion contributes to the development of good feelings, good taste, and a correct understanding of the musical works being performed.

An important method of organizing children's musical activity is exercise. In order to develop an aesthetic attitude to music, to arouse interest in it, the need to communicate with sound images, it is necessary to teach children to act actively, listen carefully, distinguish and compare the characteristic features of sound, the originality of rhythm, and capture nuances. This work is carried out consistently - day after day, year after year. Mastering the initial skills of perception and performance enriches the sense of beauty, develops initiative, the desire to act independently.

V. A. Sukhomlinsky, noted that sometimes you have to wait for years, so that one day the heart of a child trembles, overflows with a sense of beauty. The great teacher wrote: "One of the

important tasks of the educator is, figuratively speaking, to give each child his own violin, so that everyone feels how music is born.”

The methods of musical education and training are unified in their pedagogical orientation, therefore training is both educative and developing. The knowledge and skills acquired by children in the learning process help them to actively express themselves in singing, dancing, playing instruments and, thus, the educational tasks of general and musical and aesthetic development are successfully solved.

Initiation to music introduces a preschooler into the world of exciting, joyful experiences, opens the way for the aesthetic development of life within the framework accessible to his age. Therefore, it is necessary to develop in preschool children the abilities that allow them to successfully express themselves in musical activities.

The leading methods of introducing preschoolers to art, to develop their aesthetic taste, understanding of beauty, are showing, observation, explanation, analysis, an example of an adult.

Display as a method is used in the initial acquaintance with the subject of aesthetic reality. Here it is important to determine the object of the show and create conditions so that the attention of children is focused on what they are shown and offered to listen to.

When using these methods, it is important that the teacher be able to show the pupils his feelings, his attitude, and master the ways of expressing feelings. The expressiveness of intonation when reading a poem, sincere delight about beautiful music, a work of art, genuine grief when meeting with negligence or a bad deed, that is, a vivid emotional manifestation by adults of their feelings serves as an active method of influencing a child, as it relies on a feature of childhood - imitation .

A dispassionate, unemotional teacher will not be able to awaken feelings and relationships in children, therefore artistry is an important professional feature of preschool teachers.

At music lessons, the teacher introduces children to the means of musical expression: tempo, dynamics, rhythm, registers, etc. Preschoolers learn to distinguish between these means in connection with the content of a piece of music.

The main means by which preschool children form musical and aesthetic consciousness and musical culture as a whole is music itself. Only music itself can evoke (or not evoke) an emotional response of the child, which is the basis of the musical and aesthetic consciousness of the individual.

Music is an effective means of forming preschoolers' emotional culture, feelings, morality, and influences the aesthetic education of children. Aesthetic education includes the formation of aesthetic tastes and aesthetic feelings. The role of music in aesthetic education is to develop in children the ability to perceive the beautiful in the surrounding reality, in works of art, in nature, in relations with people, to distinguish really beautiful from the ugly.

Thus, music is one of the most basic, significant means in the artistic and aesthetic education of preschool children.

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